

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of N-Methylmorpholine by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate[III] Ion

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The kinetics of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion oxidation of N-methylmorpholine in aqueous alkaline medium at constant ionic strength has been studied at four temperatures. The data show that the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to each of the hexacyanoferrate(III) ion, N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion. The energy of activation and entropy of activation have been calculated to be 13.84 KCal/mole and -23.81 e.u. respectively. The net rate of oxidation of N-methylmorpholine as measured by the consumption of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion, is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [\text{M}][[\text{OH}^-][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}]$$

THE authors¹⁻² have suggested that alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ion simply acts as an electron abstracting reagent in redox reactions. However, Speakman and Waters³ have suggested a different paths of oxidation of aldehydes, ketones and nitro-paraffins. Singh and coworkers⁴⁻⁵ while discussing the oxidations of formaldehyde, acetone and ethyl methyl ketone have suggested that the oxidation takes place via an electron transfer process resulting in the formation of a free radical intermediate. The present study aims at finding out a suitable mechanism for the oxidation of N-methylmorpholine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ions on the basis of kinetic results.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data for the oxidation of N-methylmorpholine by aqueous alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ion at constant ionic strength and at four temperatures are given in Tables 1-2. The constant value of pseudo first order rate constant k_1 (Table 1) shows that the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. This was further confirmed by the standard first order plot between $\log(a-x)$ and time ($a-x$) = remaining concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion). Pseudo first order rate constants obtained at different concentrations of both N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion were directly proportional to the concentrations of N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion respectively showing thereby first order dependence of the reaction on each N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion. This was also confirmed by constant value of second order rate constant k_2 given in the last column of the Table 1. Second order rate constants were calculated for N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion by dividing k_1 values with the concentrations of N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion respectively. It was observed that the ionic strength of the medium has a positive effect on the rate of the reaction. The effect of dielectric constant on reaction rate was also

Materials and Method :

The sample of N-methylmorpholine (Fluka Grade) was used without any further purification. Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), ferrous ammonium sulphate and sodium hydroxide used were S. Merck (G. R.) grade. Other chemicals used were sodium chloride B.D.H. (A.R.), Ferrouin E. Merck and methyl alcohol (B.D.H.). The rate of oxidation was determined titrimetrically by usual method⁴.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was obtained by taking excess of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) over N-methylmorpholine to interact 1.2 M NaOH at 35°. The results showed that eighteen moles of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) were consumed per mole of N-methylmorpholine and accordingly the stoichiometry may be represented as follows :

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING REACTANTS ON RATE OF REACTION

Temp, °C	[K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆] × 10 ³ M	Ionic Strength (μ)=1.512M			k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹		k ₂ × 10 ³ 1 mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
		[N-Methyl- morpholine × 10] M	[OH ⁻] × 10 M	Calculated	Graphical		
40	1.00	1.00	12.0	10.74	10.59	-	
40	1.33	1.00	12.0	9.87	9.58	-	
40	1.67	1.00	12.0	9.23	8.64	-	
40	2.00	1.00	12.0	9.15	8.69	-	
40	2.50	1.00	12.0	8.52	8.23	-	
40	3.33	1.00	12.0	8.78	8.26	-	
40	4.00	1.00	12.0	8.56	8.37	-	
40	5.00	1.00	12.0	8.58	8.15	-	
30	2.00	1.00	12.0	3.95	-	-	
35	2.00	1.00	12.0	6.03	-	-	
45	2.00	1.00	12.0	12.44	-	-	
40	2.00	0.50	12.0	5.51	-	11.05	
40	2.00	0.67	12.0	6.35	-	9.52	
40	2.00	0.80	12.0	7.31	-	9.14	
40	2.00	1.00	12.0	9.15	-	9.15	
40	2.00	1.33	12.0	11.15	-	8.38	
40	2.00	1.50	12.0	12.60	-	8.40	
40	2.00	2.00	12.0	16.13	-	8.01	
40*	2.00	1.00	2.50	2.90	-	1.16	
40*	2.00	1.00	4.00	4.40	-	1.10	
40*	2.00	1.00	5.00	5.61	-	1.12	
40*	2.00	1.00	6.00	6.92	-	1.15	
40*	2.00	1.00	8.00	8.89	-	1.11	
40*	2.00	1.00	10.00	11.40	-	1.14	

*μ=2.012 × 10⁻¹M

studied by employing different concentrations of methanol-water mixture and it was observed that an increase in methanol concentration has a retarding effect on the reaction rate (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D)

Vol % Methanol	D	k ₁ × 10 ³
0	78.50	9.15
5	72.76	6.17
10	70.68	4.90
15	68.62	4.18
20	66.52	3.23
25	64.38	2.51

[K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³M, [N-Methylmorpholine]=1.00 × 10⁻¹M, [NaOH]=1.20M, μ=1.512 × 10⁻¹M and Temp. 40° C

In the light of above observations, the probable mechanism of oxidation may be considered as follows :

Products... (ii)

The rate of oxidation of N-methylmorpholine can be expressed by rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion concentration as shown in step (ii) i.e.,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{-3}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{-3}][\text{M}^-] \dots \text{(I)}$$

The net rate of oxidation of morpholine thus can be

obtained on substituting the value of $[M^-]$ from step (i) in equation (I) and is given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{M}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}]}{k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + [k_2] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}]} \quad \dots \text{ (II)}$$

where M is the substrate.

If the value of k_2 is of low magnitude such that $k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}] \ll k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ exists, the equation (II) becomes

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1} [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [\text{M}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-3}] \quad \dots \text{ (III)}$$

The observed first order dependence of the reaction on each hexacyanoferrate(III) ion, N-methylmorpholine and hydroxide ion concentration is obvious from the rate equation (III). The rate determining step (ii) involves interaction between two anions and in such reactions a positive salt effect is expected which is in agreement with our observations. This was further confirmed by the negative slope⁶ of the plot of $\log k_1$ versus $1/D$ where D is dielectric constant of the medium.

The free radical formed is probably fast oxidised with alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ion to intermediate products which undergo further oxidation to oxalic acid and the other products. In most of the oxidation reactions hexacyanoferrate(III) ion resembles the copper(II) which involves free radical⁷⁻⁹ formation and rapidly oxidises it. The Fe(III)-Fe(II) system, which has higher redox potential than Cu(II)-Cu(I), substantiates better possibility of the rapid oxidation of the free radicals with hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in the alkaline medium and the rapid oxidation of the radicals might completely mask the polymerization test. Some times vinyl

compounds themselves are oxidised under the experimental conditions used and the test for the free radicals¹⁰ fails. Moreover, no spectrophotometric test for complex formation was observed. Oxalic acid was identified by chromatographic technique.

The values of energy of activation and entropy of activation are 13.84 K Cal/mole and -23.81 e.u. respectively. The high negative value of entropy also supports the proposed mechanism involving two negatively charged ions.

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